

**A STUDY ON RMSA IN QUANTITY DEVELOPMENT OF SECONDARY
EDUCATION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KALIABOR
EDUCATION BLOCK OF NAGAON DISTRICT ASSAM.**

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1. INTRODUCTION: Rashtiya Madhamik Siksha Abhiyan (RMSA) is a centrally sponsored scheme for universalisation of secondary education. RMSA is one of the most recent steps taken by government of India for development of secondary level of education. The main purpose of RMSA is that to give secondary education to all students up to class X. The main objective of this scheme is that to enhance access and to improve quality of secondary education. Education is such an opportunity for empowering people with skill and knowledge to develop overall quality of life. Education is human right itself. Education helps a child to develop his power of mind in a holistic manner. Keeping in view the importance of education the government of India has taken several initiatives such as lunched various policies, schemes namely Sarva Siksha Abhiyan for universalisation of primary education and Rashtiya Madhamik Siksha Abhiyan for universalisation of secondary education etc for the growth and progress of economy the country.

1.1 MEANING OF THE TERM USED: RMSA is a scheme of the government of India for Universalisation of access to and improvement of quality of education at the secondary stage. RMSA is a shared scheme of the Central and state government to achieve Universalisation of secondary education viz. standards IX and X and to contain dropout after elementary education. This scheme was launched on second March, 2009 with the objective to enhance access to secondary education and to improve its quality

OBJECTIVES OF RMSA:

- ✓ This scheme tries to improve quality education at secondary level.
- ✓ This scheme helps to provide a secondary school within a reachable distance of any habitation which should be 5 km for secondary schools and 7-10 km for higher secondary schools.
- ✓ This scheme gives ensure universal access of secondary education by 2017 (Net

Enrolment Rate of 100%) and Universal retention by 2020)

- ✓ Its helps to provide access to secondary education with special reference to economically weaker sections of the society, educationally backward, girls, differently abled and other marginalized categories like SC, ST, OBC and Minorities.
- ✓ The objective of this scheme is to upgrade Middle Schools into High Schools.
- ✓ The other objective of this scheme is to remove, gender, socio-economic and disability barriers.
- ✓ Universal retention by 2020.

RMSA gives importance on Equity, Quality, Coverage of the scheme, physical facilities, provided by the school etc.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study the factors such as, number of students, number of passed students, number of male students, number of female students of 5 schools koliabor block of Nagaon District.

1.3 NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE:

The present study on Rashtiya Madhamik Siksha Abhiyan (RMSA) is very important and significant in secondary Education. Secondary education is the root of higher education system. RMSA is such a scheme which helps in universalisation of secondary education. Without secondary education a child can't not develop his personality properly. This study helps to know about RMSA and enrollment of secondary education of koliabor Block of Nagaon District.

1.4 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM: The present study has been entitled as "A study on RMSA in Quantity development of secondary education with special reference to Kaliabor Education Block of Nagaon District Assam.

1.5 DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

- The study has delimited in male and female enrolment, number of total enrolment, number of passed students of Class X.
- With regard to district, the study has delimited to the kooliabor block of Nagaon district of Assam.

2. REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE: The review of earlier studies helps to avoid unnecessary duplication of the study, provides assistance in formulating research problem, specifying objectives, , developing theoretical background, use of proper methodology and drawing meaningful conclusions.

With these objectives in mind, effort has been made to present the review of related studies. Although it is beyond the capacity of the researcher to gather all the related information about

the works already done due to storage of time, a brief review of related studies is made as given below.

Gehlot S and Balya S (2015) conducted a study on Panorama of girls' literacy in Rajasthan and their collaborative approaches for improvement through Rastriya Madhamik Siksha Aviyan (RMSA). This study mainly emphasized on girls' education, dropout rate, male female ration, opportunity of school education of Rajasthan.

Deb Dr P and Das P (2014) conducted a study on an Appraisal about Rashtriya Madhamik Shiksha Abhiyan from students of Uttar Dinajpur District of West Bengal. The objective of study is to examine different variables of education.

Sangeeta and kumar Dr J (2013) conducted a study on Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan Promoting Innovations under the Scheme of RMSA .The objectives of this study is to enhance access and to improve quality secondary education.

Sangeeta and kumar Dr J (2013) conducted a another study on Provision for Girls,SCs ,STs and OBCs in Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan.

Das Dr. K (2016) carried out a study on Development of Secondary Education in Sixth Scheduled Areas of Assam with special reference to Karbi Anglong District. This study mainly gave importance on role of Rashtriya Madhamik Siksha Abhiyan to develop secondary education in Karbi Anglong District.

3. METHODOLOGY: Methodology is the context of the study refers to the approach to be adopted with respect to the population and sampling design, tools of data collection and techniques of treating data. The researcher used survey method for present study for collecting information from various high schools.

3.1 POPULATION AND SAMPLE: As population the present study is delimited to 1 block of Nagaon District.

Considering the feasibility, the study has taken to only 5 schools of Kaliabor Education Block of Nagaon District. In this way, the study included quantity of secondary education of some selected schools during the period of 2012 to 2016. This study involves gender (male, female), number of total and pass students.

TOOL: The researcher used a self structured interview schedule for collecting various information from different school. The interview schedule consisted of different questions relating to the objectives of the study.

3.2 PROCEDURE OF DATA COLLECTION: The researcher visited the office of RMSA Nagaon, Inspector of School and different higher secondary schools in Kaliabor town as a primary source. The present study is based on secondary data also. The necessary data and

information were collected from MHRD Reports, Journals, and Books etc. Some related information were gathered from different websites like shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in, assam.ac.in etc.

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

According To Objective 1: To study the factors such as, number of students, number of passed students, number of male students, number of female students of 5 schools of kaliabor block of Nagaon District.

Table no 1: Data of Kaliabor Girls HS School

CLASS-X						
Name of School	Question	YEAR 2012	YEAR 2013	YEAR 2014	YEAR 2015	YEAR 2016
Kaliabor Girls HS School	Number of total students	58	54	53	56	59
	Number of passed students	50	54	48	54	41
	Number of male student	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
	Number of Female student	58	54	48	54	41

Fig 1 graphical representation of data of Kaliabor Girls HS School

From the above table1 and figure1 it is seen that there are 58 numbers of students and out of 58 students number of passed students was 50 and 8 was failed in 2012. And number of total female students 54 and out of 54 all was passed in 2013. In 2014, total number of students was 53 and 48 passed and others failed. In 2016, total 59 female students and 41 were passed and 18 failed. All are female students. There are some dropout students from 2014 to 2016.

Table 2: Jakhlabandha H.S School

CLASS-X						
Name of School	Question	YEAR	YEAR	YEAR	YEAR	YEAR
		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Jakhlabanda H.S School	Number of total students	64	48	57	49	50
	Number of passed students	41	43	39	32	29
	Number of male student	41	43	39	32	29
	Number of Female student	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----

Fig 2: Bar Diagram representing decade wise No of students of Jakhlabandha H.S School

From the above table2 and figure2 shows that there are are 64 number of students in 2012, 48 number of students in 2013, 57 number of students in 2014, and 49 number of students in

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2015 and 50 number of students of class X in 2016 of Jakhalabandha H.S School of koliabor block. All are male students. Again out of 64 students number of passed students was 41 and rest was failed in 2012. And no of total students 48 and out of 48 43 was passed in 2013. In 2014, total no of students was 57 and 39 passed and others failed. In 2016, total 50 students and only 29 were passed and 21 failed. All are male students. There are some dropout students from 2012 to 2016.

Table 3: Kuworitol High school

CLASS-X						
Name of School	Question	YEAR 2012	YEAR 2013	YEAR 2014	YEAR 2015	YEAR 2016
Kuworitol high school	Number of total students	59	54	96	70	91
	Number of passed students	59	53	94	67	91
	Number of male student	30	31	56	38	48
	Number of Female student	29	22	38	29	43

Fig 3: Bar Diagram representing decade wise No of students of Kuworitol High school.

From the above table3 and figure3 shows that there are 59 total number of students and out of 59 30 male and 29 female students and all students passed in 2012, Again 54 total numbers of students, out of 54 students 31 male and 22 female and only one student failed in 2013. Total 96 number of students and among them 56 male and 38 female students and out of 96 students 94 passed in 2014, and 70 number of students, among 38 male and 29 female in 2015. And 91 numbers of students, out of 91 students 48 male and 43 female of class X in 2016 of Jakhalabandha H.S School of koliabor block. Only 67 students passed in 2015 out of 70. In 2016 cent percentage passed.

Table 4: Kuthori H.S School

CLASS-X						
Name of School	Question	YEAR	YEAR	YEAR	YEAR	YEAR
		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Kuthori HS School	Number of total students	19	131	116	113	131
	Number of passed students	19	47	25	26	19
	Number of male student	10	27	17	18	12
	Number of Female student	9	20	8	8	7

Fig 4: Bar Diagram representing decade wise No of students of Kothari H.S School.

From the above table4 and figure4 the researcher found that under Kuthori HS School 19 number of students in class X , out of 24 students 10 male and 9 female students ,all were passed in 2012, and out of 131 number of students 27 male and 20 female and rest are dropout students, among them only 47 passed in 2013, again 116 number of students and out of 116 ,only 25 students passed in 2014, and 113 number of students, among them only 26 students passed in 2015 and 131 number of students and only 19 passed of class X in 2016 of Kuthori HS School. In Kuthori HS School dropouts' rate is very high.

Table 5: Sollong High School

CLASS-X						
Name of School	Question	YEAR	YEAR	YEAR	YEAR	YEAR
		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Sollong High School	Number of total students	95	82	86	76	84
	Number of passed students	55	48	52	45	56
	Number of male student	29	27	33	24	32
	Number of Female student	26	21	19	21	24

Fig 5: Bar Diagram representing decade wise No of students of Sollong High School.

From the above table5 and figure5 the researcher found that there are total 95 students and among them 29 male and female students in 2012.out of 95 students only 55 students passed, rest was failed. In 2013 there are total 82 students, among them 27 male and 21 female and out of 82 only 48 students passed. Again in 2014, there are total 48 students and among them

33 male and 19 female students. In 2015 there are 76 students ,out of 76 students,24 male and 21 female, and only 45 students passed in that year. Again in 2016 there were 84 students, out of them 32 male and 24 female students, only 56 students passed in that year. The pass percentage is less of Sollong High School of koliabor block.

From above analysis we found that among 5 schools of koliabor block only Kuthori Higher secondary school has highest number of students and koliabor Girls H.S School has less number of students of class X during 2012 to 2016.

Educational Implications:

- Curriculum should includes vocational subjects at secondary levels so that its helps students real life situations.
- There are many private schools where medium of instruction is only English. Government or school administration should emphasized student's academic achievements through using their own language i.e. mother tongue. So that students can improve their potentialities, capabilities in their own way.
- The government should give importance on improvement of infrastructure facilities of each and every secondary school. So those students are willing to study in schools
- Enrollment of student in secondary schools can be increase through various campaigns in our society especially in the slums areas of Assam.
- Inspired of providing intensives such as textbook, uniforms, midday meals etc by the government still various social problems are arising such as child lab our, child marriage etc .The government should be very much strict regarding this current problems and should take steps, intensives such as scholarships, residential schools for child with proper care and protection etc.

Conclusion:

RMSA is a comprehensive program of the Government of India to change the scenario of secondary school education in the country. Its gives focus on access, quality and equity. In order to meet the challenges of unversalisation of secondary education and implementation of RMSA in its true spirit, there is a need to understand the existing ground realities with respect to the preparations made by the states in terms of planning, teacher training, infrastructure, logistics, administrative set up, etc. RMSA helps to take secondary education for all children age group 14-18.

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